

ARTS

DENIS YAROVY'S INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE SOUND OF THE MONGOLIAN MORIN KHUUR INSTRUMENT

Otgonjargal Gurjav,

Ph. D., Candidate,

Mongolian National University

Saranchimeg Khandsuren

Ph. D.,

Erdenechimeg Luvsannorov Sc.D.

Abstract

This article discusses, to a certain extent, in today's musicology how the traditional construction and sound of the Morin khuur used by Mongolians are related to the Soviet master Denis Yarovoy. His work's value and innovative reforms have not been studied much. This is the main reason why we have chosen this topic for research.

Since 1967, Soviet expert Denis Yarovoy has conducted musical experiments on musical instruments to make the sound of the leather-carved Morin khuur handed down by the Mongolians equal to the music of the smooth music system. He created a new model standard for musical instruments. However, he is almost forgotten today, and his research article is based on this issue.

Keywords: Morin khuur, wooden body, new tuning, experiments

The sound of the double-string bowed Morin khuur, which the Mongolians developed, was originally played near the fire in the homes of early Mongolians, which was necessary for setting the tone. Given this, a wooden body is needed as the instrument becomes its musical journey to the concert stage.

In his memoirs, renowned composer S. Gonchigsumla mentioned, *"In 1937, while working as a veterinarian in Luu's sum of the Umungovi province, I compared the khuur with Russian instrument mandolin and attempted to play the fiddle in C key and change it to G, and C"* Music researcher J. Enebish noted this.

In the 1940s, when the Mongolian state invited the expert mentor B.V. Smirnov from the Soviet Union, the folk musicians of the central theater of Mongolia learned the modern art of music notations, recorded folk music on the music sheet, and studied classical musical instruments. He removed the method of how, in the past, Mongolians played traditional folk music by arranging the singers' voices. *"In Mongolian national music, F and B flat keys were set, which made it easier to play folk and classical music."* This is B.F. Smirnov's attempt to establish a tempered tone for traditional Mongolian musical instruments.

Composer L. Murdorj, who was the artistic director of the State Folk Song and Dance Ensemble of Mongolia, noted in his memoirs: *"The most difficult thing was to balance the power of the orchestra's voices, set the tone, and create orchestration of the music."* (Enebish, 2019:78). Also, when Mongolian musicians were on tour to a foreign countries with hot and humid conditions to participate in an international art festival, traditionally made Morin khuur and other musical instruments' leather drums would often stretch due to moisture, resulting in weakened tone, and the skins would crack when they dried. Therefore, at that time, Mr. L. Murdorj noticed that the key of the Mongolian flute instrument was not in harmony with others. He

tried to tune in the fourth interval to smooth the musical imitation and set the key correctly.

At the request of the Minister of Culture of Mongolia, L. Sosorbaram, and Deputy Minister, Ch. Lodoydamba, by the invitation of Tsedenbal Filatova, Denis Yarovoy, a renowned Soviet musical instrument luthier/master, was invited to work in Mongolia from the Soviet Union from 1967 to 1968. He familiarized himself with the traditional Mongolian musical instruments and carefully studied their sound and development. He paid attention to the smoothness of other musical instruments, such as the Morin khuur, as well as the structure and sound of the music.

D. Yarovoy, who was invited to work in Mongolia at that time, wrote in his report in 1968, *"For the past five years, Mongolians have been working on updating traditional music instruments such as Morin khuur, huuchir, and yatga, but due to the lack of knowledge and experience, they did not know how to improve. From this, it is clear that attempts to improve musical instruments' sound and music's diapason were made five years ago"*. According to D. Yarovoy's note, *"Leather khuur is closely related to the life and culture of Mongolians. Its soft, oily, and rich sound can be heard quite loudly in the circle of listeners in the home, but the sound was not enough for the orchestra's sound in a large concert hall"*. This testifies that there was a need for changes in the Morin khuur instrument. For the Morin khuur to endure unfamiliar climates, the leather body of the Morin khuur was replaced with a wooden body, and the overall design was changed. Also, there was a need to improve the timbre quality of the instrument. This reformed Morin khuur to play the same role as the Western violin and cello in modern orchestras.

Today, Mongolian Morin khuur makers make their instruments in two main ways. These include a Morin khuur with a traditional design made of leather and a Morin khuur made of a wooden body. The efforts

of Mongolians to protect their traditional art and express their nationalism are of great interest to Mongolian ethnic music groups today. There is a growing trend to play with the leather khuur to produce more traditional Mongolian melodies and sounds. However, professional performing artists still use the wooden

body Morin khuur. E. Egshiglen's undergraduate research work written in 2018 noted that "each instrument maker has own detailed development principles" and cited Z, X, and O tuning principles as examples (E. Egshiglen. 2018:37, 38).

Master B. Enkhbold's Z tuning principle

Master P. Baigaljav's X tuning principle

Master D. Tuvshintur's tuning principle

From this, it can be assumed that modern luthiers and Morin khuur craftsmen's principle of khuur tuning is based on a model that D. Yarovoy obtained based on his experiments. D. Yarovoy concluded in his report, "I do not doubt that this updated model will be further developed in detail by the instrument makers of Mongolia, whom I have worked with and taught for a year. The

orchestra musicians and soloists will have to confirm it in the end. In the first stage, all the experimental work was done only in practice". It is believed that this report, which is kept in the National Archives of Mongolia, confirms that D. Yarovoy essentially reformed the traditional Mongolian music instrument-making process.

Leather body khuur created by the "Mongolian Khuur Center"

Some studies of folk music instrument craft show the Mongolian Master B. Enkhbold's "Z-shaped Morin khuur" (O. Battugs, 2018:50). This is to put against the development of D. Yarovoy's newly created khuur tune.

Also, Mongolia has approved the standards for the design of the khuur in 2022 by the Bureau of Standard Organization of Mongolia. For example, Since masters/artisans began a wooden body khuur, dozens of Mongolian instrument makers have tried making this instrument professional and standardized and have set a single size for the khuur. The following results were obtained from this.

Morin Khuur Bridge: There are two khuur bridges: upper and lower. The lower or large bridge is

about 3.8 cm high and about 7.3cm wide, while the upper or smaller bridge is about 2.2 cm high and 3 cm wide.

Morin khuur ears: The ear or a tuner is about 15 cm. The headstock is about 77 cm, and the practical, playable size is about 44 cm.

Morin khuur body: The body of the morin khuur is trapezoidal; the upper part is 20 cm, the lower part is 28 cm, the height is 32 cm, and the distance between the sides is about 10 cm.

This specifies the basic size of the Morin khuur. Depending on the height, width, and size of the player, the size of the Morin khuur can vary. However, this design does not completely align with the original design made by D. Yarovoy.

Therefore, through this research, we have studied D. Yarovoy's original design and emphasized that this

design is the basis of today's Mongolian music makers. We consider it necessary to study it in detail. In addition, we believe it is moral to celebrate the initial design made by D.Yarovoy and its historical significance for developing modern Mongolian musical instruments.

This article aims to study the innovations and reforms introduced by Denis Yarovoy in constructing the morin khuur, a traditional Mongolian musical instrument. We tried to analyze in detail what his design ideas were based on and the results of his experiments to clarify how all his efforts influenced modern Morin khuur.

The VII International Festival of Morin Khuur Producers was organized in 2024, and many domestic and international instrument makers participated. Morin khuur-making and performing competitions were held, which showcased traditional and modern instrument-making and novel designs. Based on this, we hypothesize that the results, ideas, and traditions of D. Yarovoy's initial experiment have been preserved in the sound of today's wooden Morin khuur.

By analyzing the work report of the Soviet master Denis Yarovoy, who worked in Mongolia from 1967 to 1968, this article aims to make it known to the public and bring it into academic circulation. D.Yarovoy's report was written in Russian in 1968 and titled "The Work Report on Acoustic Construction of Morin khuur and Argal huuchir." It has two parts, is typewritten, and has 63 pages. From this report, we collected and processed only the information related to the Morin khuur and used it as the research material for this article.

In writing the article, we used historical comparisons of music science and the method of analyzing and summarizing original texts. In addition, we tried to study social and cultural features, conditions, and causes through observational and fact-analysis methods.

Before comparing these masters, looking at a brief biographical page about them would be better. Soviet violin master crafter Denis Yarovoy was born in 1921 to the family of Vladimir Yakovlevich Shevchenko, an immigrant from Trieste, Italy, who was an acoustic engineer and violinist. His biography is extraordinary. He is the only Russian master who won a gold medal at the International Viola Makers Competition in 1959 in Italy, Ascolin-Picheno. Denis Yarovoy is a master who discovered the basic principles of making musical instruments of the old Cremona masters and translated them into scientific language. He developed the so-called "Stradivarian Secret" technology to accurately adjust the violin's body's surface, creating a unique harmonic pitch simulation.

Russian musician Vladimir Kalashnikov said in an interview that he studied with D. Yarovoi from 1974 to 1990: "The violin began to develop its current appearance and sound in the middle of the 18th century. The Italians created their know-how to make the music sound beautiful, later known as the "Stradivarian secret. By the way, the first person to solve this secret was my teacher, Denis Yarovoi."

He mentions that Antonio Stradivari (1644-1737) lived in Cremona, northern Italy. There are about 650 instruments made by the hands of masters worldwide. It is widely believed that the unique sound of Antonio

Stradivari's instruments cannot be confused with any other master's creation and is an inimitable value. For centuries, musicians, violinists, engineers, and scientists have tried to unravel the secrets of the great Italian master's violin music, structure, and musical composition but have not yet fully unraveled it.

We believe that D. Yarovoy, a world-renowned master with such experience and reputation, absorbed his skills in Mongolian music instruments from 1967 to 1968. Therefore, it is proposed to include his name, considering that the standard this person first tested is still being followed.

During his work in Mongolia, he initiated many innovative projects. It includes:

1. The invention of musical instrument-making tools was first introduced.

2. The sound system has been provided with a technological model based on scientific experiments.

3. The sound quality of trees grown in our country has been determined, and standards have been set.

4. According to his report, ten people were trained in music making: Buuran, Goschii, Samdan, Jagdai, Agwaandorj, Indree, Baatar, Maluu, Badarch, and Jugder (Yarovoy, 1968:8).

5. He wrote a report on all his work, now stored in the National Central Archives of Mongolia.

Denis Yarovoy, in addition to the size and sound of the Morin khuur, aimed to improve the unique beauty of the external design and the quality of sound timbre and to create a musical instrument that would meet the requirements of modern musicians and listeners. In doing so, it echoes the violin style of the famous A. Stradivarius. That is how Yarovoy created the wooden-bodied Morin khuur we know today. When he made the instrument, he met famous Mongolian musicians, People's actors G. Jamyran, L. Murdorj, B.Damdinsuren, B. Renchin, scientists, morin khuur players, composers, and learned about the features and history of traditional Mongolian music. The master noted that these meetings were important to him in creating a national style.

As his report shows, D. Yarovoy tried to maintain a particular traditional style while changing the structure and sound of the morin khuur. He wrote in his report that "*Mongolians have long respected morin khuur as a powerful and magical instrument. Therefore, many customs exist, such as where and when to play the khuur and how to place it. For example, it is forbidden to put in a child's bed because it disturbs the child's sleep at night; if the khuur is played at night, the spirit calls to the sky, and in the Gobi Desert, it is customary to recite prayers with the sound of the Morin khuur. Also, there is a tradition of using the instrument when dealing with animals to make promises to mothers who have rejected their offspring. If someone plays the Morin khuur when visiting a family, it shows respect for the hosts. Therefore, mastering this musical instrument became one of the essential goals that a person should get for himself. This led him to focus on keeping the traditional timbre and sound of the khuur and making it cleaner. Therefore, when starting the development of sound in the first model, the body was changed, and what cannot be changed is the shape of the body of the*

instrument, the size of the neck, and the number of strings”.

Musicologist Dr. L. Erdenechimeg noted the sound features of the Morin khuur: *“The primary order of sounds of the Morin khuur is very different from the basic order of sounds in the West. The primary pitch of the basic order of the khuur starts with F, and not C, which covers the entire sound relatively high, and the nature of the melody is in flat keys”*.

Famous master D. Yarovoi noted: *“All the opposite points of the two soundboards of the khuur were added with seven basic sounds and two additional sounds. F and G are placed in the lower part of the lower deck, and E and F are in the upper part. The height of the natural frequencies of both decks correlates well with their dispersion characteristics. I’ve made my violin, viola, and cello instruments. This general law of the ancient masters to adjust the order of the sound in many colors was changed to fit the shape, material, and unique sound of the khuur”*. In doing so, to adapt the traditional khuur to modern standards, traditional sounds or folk songs were kept, and to preserve the clarity of the sound, they were used and newly added. It produces a smooth, bright, and beautiful imitation of a khuur close to that of a classical instrument.

While working on the tone development of Morin khuur music, D. Yarovoy defined the methodology of experimental research and its stages and recorded it in his report. He worked on the sound and tone of the music, which are structural elements that can only improve and change the sound’s acoustic properties without losing the Morin khuur’s traditional appearance. He tried to determine the types of wood used to make musical instruments, their combinations, and the physical and mechanical properties of trees grown in Mongolia. He used them to make the top and bottom decks of the instrument.

D. Yarovoi noted that *“using their empirical experience, the masters of music instruments have determined from century to century the types of wood and their combinations, which gives the best results for the creation of violins, violas, cellos, guitars, and pianos.”* On page 23 of his report, he says, “Researchers and some famous masters have developed recommendations for technological development. Their proposals mainly depend on the thickness rules to use at different points of the deck and the table of weight ratios. They are O. Mockel (1869-1937) and B. A. Yankovsky (1905-1973). According to Yarovoi, most Soviet masters chose a more effective of tuning the music, called “настройка.” The researcher who first mentioned the importance of adjustment was F. Savart (1791-1841), who discovered that the scale of Stradivarius’s instruments could be adjusted in seconds. German masters and physicists such as Grossmann and Migge studied soundboard tuning. Still, the most interesting hypothesis related to tuning was put forward in Russia by A.I. Lehman, A.D. Leontiev, and V. Larionov. This report clarifies that Soviet string instrument makers used a method of “tuning” the pitch or soundboard of their instruments at intervals.

In addition to the acoustic issues, Yarovoi thought about the appearance of the new Morin khuur. In addition, it was understood that small structural elements should be developed. Since it was an impossible task to transfer the structure inspired by the violin wholly, thanks to the advice of the O. Tsevegjav in creating the shape of the hole, as well as a bridge, the trough, the study of decoration and the elements of the Mongolian bowIt has been concluded that it is more reasonable to derive the shape of the Mongolian dragon in the shape of the hole.

As for the bridge design, the old horseshoe design was acoustically unreliable because it was too rigid for sound acoustics and lacked inertial resistance, which is so essential for a large deck. It is believed to have had something to do with the khuur’s leather body. This is because when installing a bridge on a wooden body, careful attention is paid to the adjustment of the sole of the bridge. There is no bass bar or sound post in the leather, and the bridge is directly mounted on the leather. Therefore, the new model of four bridges, which consists of a system for increasing the dynamic range of the sound used by Yarovoi, corrected the weakness of the old model and made it possible to transmit the vibration of the string entirely. (D. Yarovoi. 1968:25).

In his report, D. Yarovoy reported that he listened to the first sample of the khuur in Moscow with his students and analyzed the sound of the new-style musical instrument, especially the volume, the external design, the power of the sound, and the bright timbre. The music experts analyzed and praised the overall smooth improvement, and the famous Morin khuur player G. Jarmyan played on this instrument.

When starting the development of sound in the original model, the shape of the music was changed, but the shape of the instrument’s body, the neck’s size, the number of strings, and the original material could not be changed. This was the main innovation that Yarovoi could do at that time.

Contemporary Mongolian instrument makers make their Morin khuur in two main ways. These include a khuur with a traditional leather design and a wooden body Morin khuur. The efforts of Mongolians to cherish their traditional art and express their nationalism are of great interest to Mongolian ethnic groups today. There is a growing tendency to perform with the conventional leather khuur to produce Mongolian melodies and sounds. However, professional performing arts organizations still use wooden body khuurs. For example, Mongolia’s Morin Khuur Ensemble and The National Music and Dance Grand Theatre Orchestra still use the fiddle with a wooden body. Therefore, there is still a debate among musicologists and critics about the use of traditional leather-tipped khuur and wooden-tipped khuur.

Currently, active experiments are being conducted in terms of tuning the instrument. They tune in F-B, or G-C, and even in E-A tune. Since 2020, a famous Morin khuur player, D. Shinetsog-Geni, has been experimenting with the E-A tune, which brings many advantages. For example, it makes it easy to tune the orchestra. Secondly, composers can compose their music directly

without thinking about conversion. On one side of the f-hole, there is a duck or supporting wood, and the other side is empty, so the sound, color, and timbre are affected. This is how the khuur makers fulfilled Yarovoy's suggestions to develop X, Z, and O shape tunes, which are still being developed. This point suggests that Denis Yarovoy's measurements were a scientific measurement and standard due to his experiments.

The research shows that the features of the structure, melody, and sound harmony of the Morin khuur instrument used by Mongolians today are directly related to the famous Russian instrument maker Denis Yarovoy. As a result of his experiments, he selected and implemented the most suitable tuning. This change has played a significant role in the development of the Mongolian National Orchestra.

A. Stradivari's violin body model was first introduced into the Morin khuur, and the successful introduction of the multi-color soundboard tuning system found in the violin became innovative. The music-making studios first implemented by Yarovoi have grown in Mongolia. In addition, B.F. Smirnov was the first to set a tune in Morin khuur in the 1940s, which became

essential for establishing the national orchestra. We conclude that D. Yarovoy's innovations and contribution to regularizing traditional Mongolian Morin khuur music are paramount for developing Mongolian music life.

Bibliography

1. Battugs O. Dissertation on a theme "Morin khuur zemsgiin duuldakhui bolon tsahilgaan dolgionii uzuuleitiin sudalгаа" 2018., Ulaanbaatar
2. Narankhuu Ch. History of Mongolian music. 2019., Ulaanbaatar
3. Smirnov B.V. Mongolian national music. 1971., Moscow
4. Enebish J. Composer Luvsanjamba Murdorj. 2019., Ulaanbaatar
5. Enebish J. Sembiin Gonchigsumlaa. 2020., Ulaanbaatar
6. Erdenechimeg L. "Morin Khuuriin arga bilgiin arvan hoyor egshiglen" 2002., Ulaanbaatar
7. Yarovoi D. "Otchet o nauchno issledovatelskoi raboty po akusticheskoi konstrutsii Morin khuura n Argal khuuchir" 1968., Moscow